

Stages of Formation and Development of General Ethnopedagogy in the Context of a Cooperative Approach

İşbirlikçi Yaklaşım Bağlamında Genel Etnopedagojinin Oluşum ve Gelişim Aşamaları

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Öz

Bu çalışmanın amacı, yazarın geliştirdiği işbirlikçi yaklaşıma dayalı genel etnopedagojinin oluşum ve gelişim sürecinin kuramsal analizidir. Bu çalışmanın konusu genel etnopedagojinin gelişim evreleridir. Bu çalışmanın sonucunda altı aşama belirlenmiş, kanıtlanmış ve ortaya konulmuştur. Bu aşamalar; bireysel olarak uçtan uca, diyalog, grup, etnik aşaması, ulusal ve noosferik (bilishküresel) aşamalarıdır. Birinci aşama kronolojik olarak insanlığın Dünya'da doğduğu günden günümüze kadar olan zamana kapsamaktadır. Bu aşamanın özü, insanın çocuk yetiştirme konusunda belli kuralları geliştirmesi, onlarla insanlığı zenginleştirilmesi ve insanların tarihsel eğitim deneyimiyle kendini zenginleştirmesidir. İkinci aşama, herhangi bir kişide çocuk yetiştirme konusundaki görüşlerini başka bir kişinin görüşleriyle karşılaştırma, bunları birlikte tartışma ve bunlar temelinde pedagojik sorunlara ilişkin kararlar alma ihtiyacının varlığıyla karakterize edilir. Etnopedagojinin oluşum ve gelişiminin üçüncü aşaması aile, klan, kabile, toplum ve mikro çevrenin faaliyetlerinin sonucudur. Bireyin kişiliğine ilişkin aynı gereksinimler vardır ve sosyo-ekonomik açıdan yaşam koşulları aynıdır. Bu grubun ortak çalışması sonucunda mükemmel insan fikri oluşur. İnsan işbirliğinin gelişiminin dördüncü aşaması olan etnik köken, ortak toprak, dil, din ve geleneklerle karakterize edilir. Pedagojik fikirler, sözlü folklor, folklor, oyunlar ve etnopedagojinin daha da gelişmesini etkileyen belirli tarihsel figürlerin ortaya çıkmasıyla birikir. Etnopedagojik işbirliğinin gelişiminin beşinci aşaması, birlik bilinci, ortak köken, dil, inanç ve sosyal-siyasal çıkarların dayanışması ile birbirine bağlı bireyler topluluğu ile karakterize edilir. Halkın eğitim deneyimini etnopedagojik bir kurama genelleştiren, önde gelen bilim insanları ve uygulayıcılardan oluşan bir eğitim kurumları ağının bulunduğu istikrarlı bir devlet sistemi ortaya çıkar. Etnopedagojinin noosferik gelişim aşamasının işbirlikçi yaklaşım açısından özü, insanların noosferin ayrılmaz bir parçası olduğu ve yaşam faaliyetlerinin her şeyden önce noosferde meydana gelen yasalar ve küresel süreçlerle tutarlı olması gerektiğidir. Bu makalenin içeriği ve sonuçları, etnopedagojik sorunların bilim insanları, öğretmenler tarafından geliştirilmesi amacıyla düzenlenen derslerde, özel derslerde, özel seminerlerde, öğretmenlere, eğitimcilere ve eğitim örgütleri çalışanlarına yönelik ileri eğitim ve yeniden eğitim kurslarında kullanılabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Etnopedagoji, Oluşum, Gelişim, Aşamalar, İşbirlikçi Yaklaşım.

Abstract

The aim of the article is a theoretical analysis of the process of formation and development of general ethnopedagogy based on the cooperative approach developed by the author. The subject of this study is the stages of development of general ethnopedagogy. As a result of this work, six stages were identified, substantiated and disclosed: individual-through, dialog-through, group, ethnic, national, noospheric. The first stage chronologically covers the time from the day of the birth of mankind on Earth to the present. The essence of this stage lies in the development of certain rules for raising children by a person, enriching humanity with them and enriching himself due to the historical educational experience of people. The second stage is characterized by the presence of a need in any person to compare his view on raising children with the view of another person, joint discussion and, on their basis, making decisions on pedagogical problems. The third stage of

formation and development of ethnopedagogy is the result of the activities of the family, clan, tribe, society, microenvironment. In them, the requirements for the individual are uniform, the living conditions in the socio-economic plan are the same. The idea of the perfect person is formed as a result of the cooperative activity of this group. The fifth stage of development of ethnopedagogical cooperation is characterized by a set of individuals connected by the consciousness of their unity, common origin, language, beliefs and solidarity of social and political interests. A stable state system with a network of educational institutions, prominent scientists and practitioners who generalized the people's experience of education into ethnopedagogical theory appear. The essence of the noospheric stage of development of ethnopedagogy from the position of the cooperative approach is that people are an integral part of the noosphere and their life activity should be consistent, first of all, with the laws and global processes that occur in the noosphere. The content and conclusions of this article can be used for further development of ethnopedagogy problems by scientists, teachers in developing lectures private courses, private seminars in advanced training and retraining courses for teachers, educators and employees of educational organizations.

Keywords: Ethnopedagogy, Formation, Development, Stages, Cooperative Approach.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the study. This study aims to theoretically substantiate the origin, formation and development of ethnopedagogy in the context of a cooperative approach.

1.2. Scientific justification for the cooperative approach. Ethnopedagogy is one of the branches of pedagogical science. Therefore, it is legitimate that, for the first time in Russia, it is taught as an academic discipline in various educational institutions: in a secondary specialized vocational institution and a higher school. In the West, there is a parental pedagogy that is identical to folk pedagogy. The institutionalization of ethnopedagogy as a scientific discipline is taking place more slowly. It took its place in the scientific structure of the Russian Academy of Sciences only after dramatic changes in our country at the end of the 20th century.

The study of the traditional pedagogical culture of many people of the Russian Federation and the CIS, the studies of domestic and foreign scientists of the past and present, and the experience of family education have allowed us to identify the stages of the formation and development of ethnopedagogy from the perspective of a cooperative approach. By "cooperative approach" is meant to research that allows us to reveal the essence, structure, and content of any phenomenon based on cooperative readiness, cooperative information, and cooperative identity of the cooperators in the course of their joint activities. Each of these concepts is interconnected and interdependent with each other: from cooperative readiness through cooperative information, cooperative education and cooperative identity to cooperative activity in which cooperative participants create common products. At the same time, cooperative reflection is manifested only at the last stage of cooperative activity. Each participant who is in a cooperative (cooperant) and in a joint activity needs information. He extracts the information he needs during communication with another person and during the discussion of the problem, clarifying and specifying it (Baymurzina, 2016, p. 24). For instance, the objectives determine the final result of cooperative activity, in our case, folk pedagogy: "to bring a child out into the world," "to educate in work," "to form a perfect person," etc. The peculiarities of folk pedagogy of different nations are manifested depending on time, space, events, and the worldview of the people.

Thus, the cooperative approach allows us to study the process of formation and development of general ethnopedagogy in a broader and deeper way than traditional periodization based on a historical approach.

2. Main part. Six stages have been identified: individual-end-to-end, dialogue-through, group, ethnic, national, and noospheric.

The *first stage (individually end-to-end)*. Chronologically, this stage covers from the day of the birth of mankind on Earth to the present day. Every person throughout his life, based on personal positive and negative experiences, comes to develop certain rules that contribute to physical and mental survival. At the same time, a person has the opportunity to choose the optimal content, methods and forms of education

from the accumulated experience of all mankind, to rethink them through his own view of the world. At the same time, historical experience is enriched by the personal experience of everyone in the formation and development of personality.

Despite the desire for self-knowledge, it was an integral part of human consciousness. Only Socrates (469-399 BC) made the formula of wisdom ("know thyself") the main part of his teaching. Socrates's philosophy, the search for ethical definitions through dialogue, was inherent in the family, the tribe of all people of all the times. Hence, we call the *second stage of the formation and development of general ethnopedagogy a dialogue-through stage*. The experience of raising a child, influencing a person of any age in order to form the required personal qualities, or to correct them, shows the constant need for an individual to compare his view with that of another person, to discuss pedagogical problems together and make decisions based on them. At this level, each of the participants in the dialogue expresses his point of view on the subject of discussion, learns to listen to the other's position, accepts it, and defends his own one. The dialogue between the two participants in the cooperation forms the basis for a dialogue between the cultures of people.

The *third stage is a group stage*. The view of a person's upbringing becomes the property of the entire group, which can be represented by a family, a separate clan, a tribe, a society, a microenvironment. The requirements for a person's personality are the same, and the living conditions are the same in socio-economic terms. The representation of an ideal person has been finalized as a result of the cooperative activity of this group. There is a division of the type of person into "human" and "non-human".

The *fourth stage is ethnic*. Most modern experts are of the opinion that "ethnicity is a form of social organization of cultural differences." A synonym for an ethnic group is a nationality that has its own territory, language, traditions, customs, and religion. At this stage of the development of human cooperation, pedagogical ideas are embedded in works of oral folk art, folklore, and games. Rituals, customs, and traditions carry a certain pedagogical burden. There are specific historical figures (founders, warriors, sesens, bards, songwriters) who are role models for the younger generations, propagators of progressive traditions of human education. History has not preserved specific names. It was not the author of the ideas that were important, but the ideas themselves. The written compilation of the experience of raising people has ensured its transmission to the present day.

The *fifth stage is national*. This stage of development of cooperation is characterized by a set of individuals connected by the consciousness of their unity, common origin, language, beliefs and solidarity of social and political interests (Akbashev, 1990, p. 398).

A stable state system with a network of educational institutions is emerging. Folk pedagogy exists in parallel with public and private schools and workshops. They mutually enrich and complement each other. This stage is characterized by the presence of prominent scientists who summarized the national experience of education and built the educational process on its basis such as, Ya.A. Komensky. The theoretical basis of folk education was developed by the Russian teacher K.D. Ushinsky. Having thoroughly studied the nature of the education of the people of Europe, he came to the conclusion that each nation has its own education system. In the article "On the moral element in Russian education," he wrote: "We should not want to invent education: education has existed in the Russian people for as many centuries as the people themselves have existed" (Ushinsky, 1894) and others. Studies on nationality in education and on national upbringing are published. They are the sources of the development of ethnopedagogy as a science.

The *sixth stage is noospheric*. Noosphere (Greek: neos – mind and sfera – ball) – the shell of the globe, where the interaction of nature and human society take place. The concept of the "noosphere" was first

given by French scientists Edouard Le Roy and Pierre Teilhard de Chardin in 1927. According to the theory of the noosphere, there is a common brain of the Earth (Dupleix, 1991, p. 45).

Ukrainian scientist V.I. Vernadsky (1863-1945), based on the philosophy of folk pedagogy about the unity of man with the natural environment, substantiated the concept of the noosphere.

Academician V.I. Vernadsky believed that man is the highest product of evolution, a cosmic being with infinite potentials of individual and historical development. Taking into account V.I. Vernadsky's ideas about the noosphere, it's believed that one of the important and constructive tasks of modern education is the formation of a new, global type of consciousness – the noosphere, which gives out the final product of human cooperation in the context of our research – general ethnopedagogy.

T.F. Akbashev, author and leader of numerous projects on the transition from the evolution of the unconscious to the evolution of the conscious, in the book "The Path of Reason" suggests a change in life strategies at all levels of the vital mind:

- "... – from life for consumption to consumption for life;
- from the cult of destruction to the cult of awakening individual and collective forces;
- from the civilization of accumulation of death to the civilization of accumulation of immortality.

For their survival, man and the people of the Earth must immediately activate the four qualities of their life potential.

The first is the sustainability of life potential.

The second is the mobility of life potential.

The third is the instrumentality of life potential.

The fourth is the ability of life potential to self-generate" (Akbashev, 2009, pp. 106-107).

When it comes to life potentials, it seems to us that general ethnopedagogy is just that. There can be no doubt here. The question is different: how to use the knowledge, technologies and developed pedagogical tools accumulated over thousands of years in it for these purposes in the conditions of a totalitarian regime, increasing callousness, and the destruction of the planet? Only the cooperation of the noospheric level can stop all this and give the human species a chance to survive.

At this stage, the planetary mind acts as one whole cooperation, in which everyone receives the necessary knowledge in the information field and distributes his own. Fast communication is facilitated by modern means of transportation, the Internet, and knowledge of foreign languages. The development of science helps to accumulate knowledge about a person and the ways of his upbringing at all times, select the best for modern conditions, summarize scientifically and return it to educational institutions and families as a pedagogical tool.

3. Conclusion. Thus, as a starting point for understanding the problems of general ethnopedagogy, we have considered one axiom and several basic facts.

The axiom is that there is no knowledge without comparison and generalization. In order to verify the truth of this statement, we turned to the development of cooperatives – groups of people, nations united to create concepts of human education. To fully understand the phenomenon, it was necessary to compare ethnopedagogy and the development of people as a cooperative.

The first fact is related to the fact that cooperation is understood as the cooperation of several individuals and ethnic groups to form the traditional pedagogical culture of people from the dawn of mankind to the present.

The essence of the second fact is that the common product of pedagogical cooperation, folk pedagogy, has a lot in common among different people, despite the difference in time and geography.

The third fact is the cooperative effect. By participating in joint activities, a person can use the strength of the team as his own.

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Etik Kurul Kararları / Ethics Committee Decisions

Bu çalışma için etik kurul belgesi gerekmemektedir.

Ethics committee approval is not required for this study.

Yayın Etiği Beyanı / Publication Ethics Statement

Bu makalenin planlanmasından, uygulanmasına, verilerin toplanmasından verilerin analizine kadar olan tüm süreçte "Yükseköğretim Kurumları Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Yönergesi" kapsamında uyulması belirtilen tüm kurallara uyulmuştur. Yönergenin ikinci bölümü olan "Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiğine Aykırı Eylemler" başlığı altında belirtilen eylemlerden hiçbiri gerçekleştirilmemiştir. Bu araştırmanın yazım sürecinde bilimsel, etik ve alıntı kurallarına uyulmuş; toplanan veriler üzerinde herhangi bir tahrifat yapılmamıştır. Bu çalışma herhangi başka bir akademik yayın ortamına değerlendirme için gönderilmemiştir.

All the rules specified in the "Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Directive" have been complied with in the whole process from the planning of this article to its implementation, from data collection to data analysis. None of the actions specified under the title of "Actions Contrary to Scientific Research and Publication Ethics", which is the second part of the directive, were not carried out. During the writing process of this research, scientific, ethical and citation rules were followed; No falsification was made on the collected data. This work has not been submitted for evaluation to any other academic publication medium.